

IMPACT OF AUTOMATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT ON UNEMPLOYMENT**Suleimanov S.***PhD student (Baku State University),
Azerbaijan, Baku***Abstract**

Unemployment is an important aspect of social problems. It can be assumed that many problems arise due to a lack of means of subsistence, and in the current world, having a job is the key to success and a means of earning income to support oneself. The advancement of automation is an inevitable development factor. Every year the world's population increases and unsolved social problems deepen. Automation is happening everywhere and at a rapid pace. Therefore, striking a balance between automation and social security is important.

Rapid development is making the situation more and more complicated. Technologies can gradually change absolutely all areas of production. People become less in demand in many areas of production (mainly the lower stratum of the population)

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It is widely accepted that technological change can lead to short-term job losses. The idea that they could lead to long-term increases in unemployment has long been controversial. Participants in the technological unemployment debate can be divided into optimists and pessimists. Optimists agree that innovation can disrupt jobs in the short term, but still believe that various offsetting effects avoid long-term negative consequences for jobs. While pessimists argue that, at least in some circumstances, new technologies could lead to a prolonged decline in the total number of workers in employment. The phrase "technological unemployment" was popularized by Keynes in the 1930s. At the same time, the issue of replacing human labor with machine labor has been discussed at least since the time of Aristotle.

Before the 18th century, both elites and common people generally had a pessimistic view of technological unemployment; however, due to the generally low levels of unemployment in the pre-modern period, the topic rarely aroused significant concern. In the 18th century, concerns about the impact of technology on jobs grew as mass unemployment grew, especially in Britain, which was then at the forefront of the Industrial Revolution. However, some economic thinkers have begun to counter these fears, arguing that overall the innovations will not have negative consequences for jobs.

These arguments were formalized at the beginning of the 19th century in the works of classical economists. In the second half of the 19th century, it became increasingly clear that technological progress was in the interests of all sectors of society, including the working class. Concerns about the negative impact of innovation have diminished. The claim that innovation will have long-term negative effects on employment has come to be called "Luddism" [1].

Changes in the nature of work take the form of its individualization and autonomization, which is due to the expansion of access of its subjects to significant amounts of information. These processes are manifested in the introduction of remote forms of employment among hired workers, the self-employed and crowdworkers, or participants in various projects on a

non-permanent basis. The introduction of digital platforms creates the prerequisites for the interaction of supply and demand subjects, as well as for the development of new and modification of traditional services, including home delivery, short-distance transportation, consulting activities, etc.

Another feature of the labor market in the context of digitalization of the economy is the increased dependence of labor activity on the technical system, since the processes of worker autonomy can be hampered by available technologies. Despite the fact that the work is individualized, the coordination of the participants' activities is carried out using digital platforms. Thus, digitalization provides work flexibility.

Digital platforms determine the dependence of participants on their inherent operating algorithms. For example, the emergence of digital platforms in the field of passenger transportation has allowed many drivers to find an independent form of activity and at the same time subjected them to the conditions determined by this platform [2].

An important feature of the world of work has become the blurring of boundaries between private and professional spaces, which is manifested in the possibility of inclusion in the labor process anywhere and at any time. This leads to a lack of restrictions on the length of the working day and working week, as well as disruptions to traditional work rhythms, which, in turn, disrupts vertical interactions and hierarchical structures, which are replaced by horizontal connections. If a hierarchical management organization presupposes a strict distribution of competencies and control over the flow of information by the leadership center, then in a network organization the availability and high speed of information flows allows employees to enter into effective interactions with outsiders and insiders.

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turn, disrupts vertical interactions and hierarchical structures, which are replaced by horizontal connections. The digital revolution is leading to a transformation of non-professional activities that are becoming collaborative (for example, the creation of Wikipedia by Internet users for free). Many activities based on open source resources and carried out by volunteers compete with classic activities. This is the case in software (Linux, Mozilla, Apache), film production, music creation, etc. At the same time, activities that were traditionally free are being commercialized (for example, renting a car on a one-time basis to a third party for the duration of a trip (Blablacar) or apartments (Airbnb). Thus, the boundary between personal and work time becomes blurred, which means a return to pre-industrial practices on a new technological basis.

The threat of technological unemployment is occasionally used by free market advocates as a justification for supply-side economics-style reforms to make it easier for employers to hire and fire workers. Conversely, it has also been used as an excuse to justify increased worker protections. Larry Summers proposes a vigorous, concerted effort to combat the "myriad of schemes" - such as tax havens, banking secrecy, money laundering, regulatory arbitrage - that allow those with great wealth to avoid paying taxes - to make it more difficult to amass vast fortunes without a reciprocal "great social contribution" " Summers proposed stricter

enforcement of antitrust laws; reducing "excessive" intellectual property protection; greater encouragement of profit-sharing systems that can benefit workers and give them a share in the accumulation of wealth; strengthening collective labor agreements; improving corporate governance; strengthening the financial regulatory system to eliminate subsidies on financial activities; easing land use restrictions that can lead to higher prices for land holdings; improving the professional training of young people and retraining of laid-off workers; increasing public and private investment in infrastructure development such as energy and transport [1].

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